

ISic2877

I.Sicily inscription 2877

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific; decree
(?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi (?)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Γ[---]
2. ἡ βουλ[ῆ·καὶ·ὁδῆμος·τῆς·]
3. λαμπρᾶ[ς·Συρακοσίων]
4. [μ]ητ[ροπόλεως ---]

Apparatus

Text after Manganaro 1993

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645271

PHI 332711

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 43.0634

Manganaro, G. 1993. Greco nei pagi e latino nelle città della Sicilia romana tra I e VI sec. d.C.. In Calbi, A., Donati, A., Poma, G.(eds.), *l'epigrafia del villaggio*. Faenza. pp. 543-594. At 583 n.102 fig.20

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